

AIMING FOR AN IMPROVED CLASSROOM INSTRUCTION ANALYZING THE EFFECT OF NEW NORMAL INSTRUCTIONAL PRACTICES OF ELEMENTARY TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

This study was to determine the improved classroom instruction and instructional practices in the new normal of elementary teachers. The data and information were obtained from different schools in Tiaong, Quezon. The survey questionnaire was used as the main instrument in gathering data needed. The frequency distributions, percentage, mean and standard deviation were the statistical tools used to describe the general information about the respondents and to determine the relationship between the independent variable and dependent variable. The following are the findings of the study: In New Normal Classroom Instruction, Mastery is the most appropriate among eight practices. For the level of Classroom Instruction as to Content Knowledge and Pedagogy, Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners, Curriculum Planning, and Assessment and Reporting, majority of the teachers were interpreted as “Proficient Teacher” This signifies that this study will help the teachers to reflect on and assess their own practices as they aspire for personal growth and Professional Development and to ensure that effective learning happens even during this crisis situation, guaranteeing that quality education is provided to DepEd Quezon Learners.

Keywords: Improve Classroom Instruction, New Normal Instructional Practices